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THE ROLE OF INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES IN INCREASING THE EXPORT POTENTIAL OF THE UZBEK ECONOMY

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Abstract: This article considers the modernization and diversification of leading industries, the introduction of modern technologies for processing raw materials and semi-finished products, targeted support for highly competitive industries in the world market, increasing the share of the processing industry in the structure of production, implementing a cluster model for the development of the textile industry, and the development of logistics and engineering infrastructure.

Key words: Industrial enterprises, modernization, diversification, technology, competition, logistics.

INTRODUCTION

During the years of independence, Uzbekistan confidently entered the world stage of light industry. By attracting local and foreign investments, establishing enterprises equipped with new modern equipment, and using advanced technologies, competitive and export-oriented finished products began to be produced. Our country's industry is developing rapidly, and its economic power and potential are increasingly recognized as a modern state. The reason is that during the years of independence, all areas of industry based on high technologies have been steadily developing in our country.

This creates the need to create new competitive advantages in the further development of the sector, which will allow expanding the specialization of the national economy in the world economic system and diversifying the structure of industrial production through the rapid introduction of innovative technologies and modern scientific achievements into industrial sectors.

ANALYSIS OF LITERATURE ON THE TOPIC

An analysis of the existing literature on marketing shows the need to improve modern marketing principles, brand promotion methods and a flexible approach to consumer requirements. In his textbook on marketing strategies, the expert R.Ibragimov states the following: "Marketing strategy is understood as the use of a model of the principles of the enterprise's behavior in the market, established for a certain period of time. With its help, the enterprise seeks to ensure its success." Many economists have been involved in the development and implementation of marketing strategies. Among them are such famous scientists as F. Kotler, David Aaker, Clayton Christensen, Seth Godin, Kevin Keller, Byron Sharp, and Jay Bayer.

While the research conducted in the field of marketing in our country for many years is based on national characteristics, it is also necessary to recognize the scientists who have made a significant contribution to the development of marketing theory. These include R.Ibragimov, Y.O.Abdullaev, A.Saliev, M.Sharifkhodjaev, D.Rakhimova, Sh.Ergashkhodjaeva, Sh.Musayeva and others..

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study used a systematic approach, marketing analysis, benchmarking, and digital metrics. Mass surveillance methods were used to collect and analyze data from social media platforms.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Currently, the most pressing issues are to increase the range and quality of goods produced, ensure their stable sales in domestic and foreign markets, increase competitiveness in a highly competitive environment, extend the life of goods, create new product designs based on market demand, strengthen the position of local goods, and ensure their brand recognition.

The modernization and diversification of leading industrial sectors, the introduction of modern technologies for processing raw materials and semi-finished products, targeted support for highly competitive industries in the world market, contributed to an increase in the share of the processing industry in the structure of production.

If in 2019 the share of the processing industry in the total volume of industrial production was 73.8%, then by 2023 it will increase to 80.3%.

In the total volume of industrial production, the volume of production of products with high added value increased in the following sectors: food, textiles, chemistry, pharmaceuticals, and others.

In 2023 alone, compared to the previous year, the growth in production volume in the processing industry amounted to 6.4%, including 40.3% in the production of basic pharmaceutical products and preparations, 34.4% in chemical products, rubber and plastic products, 20.9% in other non-metallic mineral products, 10.8% in food products, beverages, tobacco products, and 9.0% in the production of textile products, clothing, and leather products.

The President of our country pays great attention to the development of the textile industry. In the past year, several decrees and resolutions have been issued to further develop this sector:

Modernization and diversification of the textile and carpet manufacturing industry is the most important condition for expanding the volume and types of finished competitive products produced in high demand in foreign markets, as well as increasing the efficiency and profitability of cotton production and processing.

Taking this into account, practical measures aimed at ensuring the further development of this sector are being consistently implemented in our country.

First of all, the existence of systemic problems related to the establishment of the production of finished products, the organization of network management, the distribution of resources and production capacities, and the lack of high qualifications of personnel lead to low profitability of cotton raw material cultivation and its processing, as well as insufficient production and export of finished products.

Adopted by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan The Decree «On Measures for the Accelerated Development of the Textile Industry» defined a set of priority measures to address existing problems, as well as expand the production of high-quality textile products and promote them to world markets.

This document identified the following important areas for further reform of the textile industry, in particular:

- increasing the share of the textile industry in the economy, increasing the volume and quality of textile products produced in the country;
- a fundamental revision of the management system of the textile industry;
- further improving the standardization and certification system in the textile industry;
- widespread introduction of advanced information and communication technologies into the network;
- implementation of a cluster model for the development of the textile industry;
- ensuring a balance in the distribution of raw material resources and the location of established industry enterprises, in close connection with the development of logistics and engineering infrastructure;
- widespread introduction of advanced innovation technologies, know-how, and design developments into the production process, localization of the production of modern models of fittings and accessories;
- radically improve the system of training, retraining and advanced training of personnel for the textile industry.

It is worth noting that this Decree is an important step in the practical implementation of the Concept of Administrative Reforms in the Republic of Uzbekistan, approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5185 dated September 8, 2017, which provides for further reduction of administrative influence on economic sectors and expansion of market mechanisms of management.

In particular, the Decree approved the “Roadmap” for the accelerated development of the textile and garment and knitwear industry in the Republic of Uzbekistan, which consists of more than 20 measures to improve the management and personnel training system, modernize the technological process and develop the

infrastructure of the production and textile industry, activate foreign economic activity, and introduce international standards in the textile industry.

«Uzbekengilsanoat» JSC, actively attracting investments, is ensuring stable growth in production and export volumes. The share of textile semi-finished products in the total volume of exports was 14.4%. The export volume in 2023 amounted to 1090 million dollars. In 2018-2023, the volume of exports of light industry products increased from 660 million dollars to 1090 million dollars, or in other words, the volume of exports increased by 1.6 times.

Today, the republic has a textile industry with a huge production potential, in its system of which about 7 thousand enterprises are effectively operating. In addition, capacities for the production of yarn in the amount of 1.4 million tons have been created, and about 60 percent of this raw material is used to meet the needs of textile enterprises of our country. If earlier only 436 organizations were included in the structure of JSC «Uzbekengilsanoat», now all enterprises and organizations of the textile industry can become members of the Association «Uzto'tsikhismsanoat».

This provides a number of advantages for local manufacturers. In particular, enterprises that are members of the «Uzto'tsikhismoat» Association are exempted from paying customs duties on imported cotton, artificial and synthetic fibers, wool, raw materials and other materials necessary for the production of textile products and not produced in the republic (except for fees for customs clearance). In addition, the «Uzto'tsikhismoat» Association is granted the right to file lawsuits in the interests of its members, to transfer complaints without paying state duty regarding decisions of state bodies and other organizations, actions (inaction) of officials in court proceedings.

An inventory of existing needs in narrow specialties at industry enterprises is being conducted and a database of authors from the Tashkent Institute of Textile and Light Industry and industry vocational colleges is being created. In cooperation with this higher education institution, short-term (part-time and evening) courses have been organized to supply specialists for the industry in such areas as spinning, weaving, sewing, dyeing and decoration, as well as to train experienced technicians working in corporate management enterprises (personnel management, state and public administration).

In particular, this year, 34 investment projects aimed at the modernization, technical and technological re-equipment of existing enterprises, and the creation of new capacities were implemented in the sector. The total cost of these projects amounted to \$356.9 million, with an export potential of \$151.7 million.

At the same time, the press conference also discussed the export indicators of the industry. It was noted that in 2023, 1.16 billion dollars worth of products are expected to be exported. Products manufactured in our country are supplied to more than 30 countries of the world. The share of products with high added value amounted to more than 40 percent.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

Marketing has become the main tool for increasing competitiveness in the world market, therefore, it is necessary for Uzbek enterprises to ensure the use of the most advanced marketing technologies. Increasing marketing efficiency is especially important in the production of woven and knitted products, which is one of the strongest sectors of the Uzbek economy. The relevance of this problem is confirmed by a number of Decrees and Resolutions adopted by our esteemed President in recent years. The need to increase marketing efficiency at enterprises formed the goal of our research conducted in our dissertation and is the basis for the following conclusions.

Uzbekistan's industrial enterprises are one of the drivers of our country's international competitiveness. In recent years, as a result of domestic processing of cotton raw materials, significant changes have occurred in the textile and clothing industry. In particular, the growth of the number of carpet weaving enterprises is leading to increased competition in the carpet market.

The uniqueness of the textile industry is that the value chain is long, requiring the joint work of several enterprises. In addition, entering foreign markets also requires the joining of forces. For this reason, we propose the widespread use of the principles of the cluster system when creating a marketing program. This involves the systematic work of raw material suppliers, logistics systems, export-import organizations, etc.

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